

**COMPARATIVE LITERARY STUDIES, HYBRID
LINGUISTICS, TRANSLATION STUDIES**

Saxibova Dilrabo Ergashevna

English teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13925350>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08th October 2024

Accepted: 12th October 2024

Online: 13th October 2024

KEYWORDS

Literary, linguistics,
translation, hybrid,
language, comparative,
study, typological.

ABSTRACT

This article aims to study a section of literary history that studies international literary connections and relations, and the similarities and differences between literary and artistic phenomena in different countries. The subject of the study often overlaps with translation studies.

Similar paths of literary development among different nations do not exclude the possibility of international contacts and mutual influences and usually intersect with them. International literary connections and interactions represent a historical category, in different historical conditions have different intensity, and take different forms.

Similarity of literary facts can be based on similarity:

- social and cultural development of peoples;
- cultural and literary contacts between these peoples.

Distinction is made between: typological analogies of the literary process and "literary connections and influences".

The premise of comparative historical literary criticism is the unity of the socio-historical development of mankind. As a result of similar social relations among different peoples, historical and typological analogies can be observed in the development of different literatures in one historical era. The subject of comparative historical study from this point of view can be:

1. individual literary works;
2. literary genres and styles;
3. features of the work of individual writers;
4. literary trends.

Typological similarities (analogies, correspondences) between national literatures as a result of similar stages of socio-historical and cultural development of peoples. They are especially evident in the early stages of socio-historical development (with the extreme doubt of any contacts): for example, the chivalric ("courtly") novel in the West in the 12th-13th centuries ("Yvain, or the Knight with the Lion" by Chretien de Troyes, "The Romance of Tristan and Isolde", "Parsifal" by Wolfram von Eschenbach) and poems of Iranian-language writers of the 11th-13th centuries ("Layla and Majnun" by Nizami, "Shahnameh" by Firdausi). Problems

of literary periodization, its dependence on social history and relative autonomy. Types of artistic consciousness: mythopoetic, traditionalist, individual-authorial, distinguished in modern literary criticism (S.S. Averintsev et al.), as the most important milestones of literary development proper. Concepts of stage (stage-wise) of literary development, accelerated development of national literature (story "Jamila" by Ch. Aitmatov). Main stages of development, literary trends, stable styles that bring together European literatures; their chronological "dispersion" in different literatures (classicism in Italy, France and Russia; symbolism in French and Russian literatures). Typological categories (genera and genre groups of works, types of ideological and emotional assessment, etc.), their role in ensuring the continuity of literary development and interaction of literatures. Typology in comparative versification. Typological convergences of literatures as an objective prerequisite for internal, creative contact links (Ch. Baudelaire and A. A. Blok; T. Gautier and N. S. Gumilev). The question of the boundaries of typological parallels. The danger of dissolving parallels based on the principle of historicism, the stage-by-stage development of literatures, in the universal structures of human behavior reflected in literature (for example, the motif of "love as suffering" in itself cannot serve as a basis for comparative research). The current state of comparative literary criticism, the possibilities and prospects of this scientific direction - in relation to structuralism, psychoanalysis (the theory of archetypes of K. Jung) and other methods that are fundamentally abstracted from socio-historical specifics.

Hybrid linguistics, a conventional term. 1) Sometimes used to denote languages mixed in the narrow sense of the word (langues mixtes, Mischsprachen), i.e. languages whose sound composition, grammatical structure and vocabulary are the result of a kind of compromise between substantially different language systems of peoples distant in their cultural level and whose emergence satisfies the needs of international communication in a narrow circle of colonization relationships (trade, work on plantations, etc.). Such are the "international" languages of the colonies - "Bich-la-Mar" of the Pacific Ocean, "Pidgin English" of the Far East, "trade jargons" of North America, etc. For more information on the economies and prerequisites for the creation of this type of G. l., see Dialect, Language. 2) A term introduced by Academician N. Ya. Marr to designate mixed languages in the special sense of the word, namely languages whose sound system reflects the simultaneous action of laws that are represented separately in other languages; for example, the Svan language is called mixed languages, part of whose vocabulary exhibits sound correspondences according to the laws of the spirant branch (represented in its pure form by the Japhetic languages of the North Caucasus), and part according to the laws of the sibilant branch (the Japhetic languages of the Kartvelian group). The following are classified as mixed languages: Abkhazian, Basque, both Proto-Armenian languages (Vaisk and Vaik), and a number of ancient languages of the Mediterranean circle (Etruscan, Chaldean, Elamite, Sumerian). See Hybridization, Japhetic Theory, Classification of Languages.

Hybridization in linguistics - a term introduced by Academician N. Ya. Marr to denote the process of formation of mixed, or hybrid languages (see). Hybridization is almost synonymous with the term "mestication". Distinguishing between the two terms (Hybridization - mixing of related languages, metication - mixing of unrelated languages) presents great difficulties. In the early stages of the development of the Japhetic theory (see), much attention was paid to the

phenomenon of Hybridization and its role in the creation of new linguistic units; in its later stages, the concept of hybridization was removed, thanks to a categorical rejection of the genealogical principle of language classification (see) and the introduction of the concept of stadiality into the typological analysis of languages. See Japhetic theory.

Translation studies, translation theory, occasionally translatology, traductology (from the French *traduction*) is a humanitarian discipline at the intersection of linguistics, communication theory, comparative literature, semiotics and sociology, studying the process and results of oral and written translation, as well as a wide range of related phenomena (for example, localization). In addition, the interests of translation studies include the ideology and social aspects of translation as an activity.

Translation studies originated as a normative, prescriptive discipline, accumulating and formulating practical recommendations for translators. In the European tradition, the conventional starting point is considered to be Cicero's treatise *De Optimo Genere Oratorum* ("On the Best Kind of Orator"), which discusses the benefits of translation from Greek for the practical preparation of an orator.

The 1950s and 1960s were marked by the emergence and rapid growth of linguistically oriented translation studies. In 1958, Jean-Paul Vinay and Jean Darbelnet wrote a comparative stylistics of French and English for the purposes of translation.

Translation studies as a scientific discipline is quite young, its history is just over 50 years old, however, for the theory of translation this period has proven to be unusually fruitful. As the main tasks of the theory of translation, A.V. Fedorov notes the following: "to trace the patterns in the relationship between the original and the translation, to generalize in the light of scientific data the conclusions from observations of individual cases of translation, to indirectly contribute to translation practice, which could draw from it arguments and evidence in the search for the necessary means of expression and in favor of a certain solution to specific problems". The main focus of translation theory is "the relationship between the original and the translation and the difference in the forms they take in specific cases requiring explanation and generalization" (*ibid.*), and the object of translation theory is "translation as a creative activity associated with language and literature and inevitably presupposing contact between two languages, the transmission of the original by means of another language".

Translation theory uses data from various sciences, including linguistics, and adapts their methods to solve its own problems. Translation studies is closely related to linguistics, literary criticism, philosophy, history, sociology, psychology and other disciplines. Depending on the problem being studied, different methods may come to the fore. For example, the study of equivalence requires the use of linguistic methods, while the solution of stylistic problems is impossible without the use of literary methods. At present, translation studies is recognized by a number of researchers as an interdisciplinary science; other researchers (for example, N.K. Garbovsky) believe that "recognizing the interdisciplinary status of translation theory is convenient only in order to avoid solving the very complex question of what is the proper subject of this science, since interdisciplinarity is nothing more than examining an object through the prism of the subjects of different sciences."

During the II Congress of Slavists in Moscow (1958), heated debates broke out between supporters of the linguistic and literary approaches to translation, the resolution of which was

a fragile consensus that translations should be studied within the framework of a special discipline, with its own set of approaches and arsenal of methods that cannot be reduced to either literary or purely linguistic ones. The first research teams engaged in translation emerged at some US universities (University of Iowa, Princeton University) in the 1960s.

In recent years, translation studies has been increasingly integrated with information technology; at the University of Mannheim, this specialty is studied at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. At the Brest State University named after A. S. Pushkin, at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, simultaneously with teaching such a technical discipline as computer translation, a classic course "Introduction to Translation Studies" is taught. Translation studies can be normative (prescribing the use of certain translation rules) or descriptive (descriptive).

References:

1. Nelson Lowry "Poetic configurations" (1988).
2. Haun Saussy "Comparative Literature in an age of Globalization" (2006).
3. Bermann Sandra "Working in the And Zone: Comparative Literature and Translation" (2009).
4. Zhirmunsky V. M., "Comparative Literary Studies and the Problem of Literary Influences" (1936).
5. Sanchez-Stockhammer Christina "Hybridization in Language" (1970).
6. Rarenko B. M., "Linguistic theory of translation". 2003.
7. Fedorov A.V. "Fundamentals of the General Theory of Translation" – M., 2002.